

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 1.1: DELIVERY OF BEST PERFORMING *ULVA* SPP. STRAINS TO ALGAPLUS FOR TESTING AT THEIR FARM

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confidential report

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Summary:

Eighty-eight strains of *Ulva* spp. have been received from the company AlgaPlus based in Portugal in March, July, and November 2023. Among those strains, seven showed a growth performance and biochemical composition like the three strains selected for growth performance during the earlier conducted EU funded GenialG project. The growth performance was evaluated first by cultivating the strains in bottles, selecting the most promising ones which were then evaluated using a high-resolution phenotyping platform based on image captures taken every five minutes. Those strains will be evaluated for resilience to low salinity and heat stress in early 2024. Those stresses are happening at the land-based cultivation facility and leading to loss of productivity.

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